

Design of a Compact Dual Band Microstrip Antenna for Bluetooth/WLAN and UWB Applications

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a compact design of a dual-band antenna is developed for Bluetooth, WLAN, and UWBs is 2.3 and 5.8 GHz respectively. This paper discusses the design and simulation of dual band microstrip antenna, for blue tooth and WLAN, at 2.4GHz and UWB at 5.6 to 6.2GHz. The dimension of the antenna was 60mm by 60mm. The design was simulated using HFSS. The return loss at 2.3 GHz is -32 DB. The bandwidth at 2.4GHz is 90Mz. The second band occurs between 5.6 to 6.2 GHz. The return loss for the said band is well below -10dB. Finally, we report the bandwidth in UWB section to be 600 MHz, making it suitable to use simultaneously for blue tooth, WLAN and UWB applications

INTRODUCTION

Microstrip antennas have been novel subjects in antenna design and theory and are being used more frequently in a numerous contemporary microwave system. By nature, among their many benefits is their ease of fabrication. Conventional integrated circuit methods, are low-profile, are conformal, readily incorporated into arrays, and with electronic parts [1]. However, microstrip antennas usually, has narrowband radiation affects, weak polarization, and low gain purity, an issue with tolerance, and a power capacity limitation. Satellites and GPS are the set-ups which required

to operate on two disparate frequencies. Actually, microstrip antennas doesn't work on two disparate single band antennas. For this researcher made different techniques [2-3]. Wireless Communication (WC) systems, compact multiband antenna has become indispensable element because of the capability to cover multiple frequency bands. In recent years wireless communication makes a huge progress, due to the growing market interest for small-scale and higher quality wireless devices [4]. For applications which used to convey information for small intervals, continually researchers trying to attain smaller size of

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multiband and broadband antennas. [5]. An example of that is (WLAN) wireless local area network L, a flexible data communication system, carryout as a replacement for wired LAN. [6]. WLAN (wireless local area network) is the popular network which is used all around the world these days. [7] WLANs use radio frequency to send and receive data, combining connectivity and user mobility. Consequently, in specific markets like manufacturing, healthcare, warehousing, academia and retail etc., WLAN is becoming more and more famous. And are also vastly known as valid and economically inexpensive conclusion for a wide range of systems that use for real-time wireless high-speed data communication. [7]. UWB (Ultra-wide band) antennas are also having a popular technology due to miniaturization, broad bandwidth, less expensive, favorable phase linearity. [8]. The UWB has large frequency range, that's why numerous frequency bands lie in UWB spectrum and WLAN frequency band which has range of 5-6GHZ frequency also lie in UWB spectrum. [9-11]. The current antenna designs are optimized for a single application i.e., for Bluetooth, WLAN and UWB. A single design which can be used for all three applications with optimized performance is not reported till date and requires an investigation.

ANTENNA DESIGN

Antenna design which can cover, Bluetooth, WLAN, and UWB is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed antenna design with dimensions

This is dual band Microstrip Patch Antenna. Initially took several designs and a new design was made by using HFSS. The FR-4 material is used for substrate with the thickness of 1.2mm. The copper material is used for patch. The parameters of the antenna are shown in the table-1

Table 1: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Size of antenna	A	60mm × 60 mm
Width	W	20mm
Feed line length	L	40mm
Length of patch	H	48mm
Diagonal length	D	24mm
Segment width	WS	4mm
Dimension of cut on ground	CG1 CG2	16×1 20×1

Figure 2: Flow char of the proposed antenna system

SOFT IMPLANTATION

By using the parameters, the design was implemented in HFSS. This is a dual band antenna which operates on two resonant frequencies. Figure 3 depicts the implemented proposed patch antenna. The frequency sweep was selected

from 1GHz to 10GHz. By validating and analyze the proposed design we finally perform the simulation.

Figure 3: Implemented antenna in HFSS

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The figure 4 shows the return loss vs frequency graph. It is evident from figure 4 that the return loss for this antenna at 2.3GHz is -31.38 and the bandwidth at 2.3 is 90 MHz, moreover the bandwidth at 5.8GHz is 6490 MHz.

This figure 5 is showing VSWR, there are different values at different frequencies, as the value at 2.3GHz is 1.1. For 5.8GHz band, it is less than 2. All VSWR values are acceptable for the said bands.

This figure 5 below shows the radiation pattern of dual band microstrip patch antenna. Figure 6 shows the three-dimensional radiation pattern of the proposed dual-band microstrip patch antenna. It exhibits a directional radiation pattern with the main lobe aligned with the +z-axis. The maximum electric field magnitude reaches approximately 5.115 mV, indicating strong radiation performance suitable for wireless applications like Bluetooth and WLAN.

Figure 7 shows the smith chart to observe impedance behavior and matching. These spirals show how impedance changes with frequency. If any part of the curve gets close to the center (low return loss, good radiation), the antenna is well matched at that frequency. Either a multi-band antenna or complex impedance behavior is indicated by the looping behavior.

Figure 4: Return loss of the proposed antenna from simulation.

Figure 5: VSWR for the proposed antenna

Figure 6: Gain of the proposed antenna.

CONCLUSION

This paper discusses the design and simulation of dual band microstrip antenna, for blue tooth and WLAN, at 2.4GHz and UWB at 3.6 to 5GHz. The dimension of the antenna was 60mm by 60mm. The design was simulated using HFSS. The return loss at 2.3 GHz is -32 dB. The bandwidth at 2.4GHz is 90Mz. The second band occurs between 5.6 to 6.2 GHz. The return loss for the said band is well below -10dB. Finally, we report the bandwidth in UWB section to be 600 MHz.

Figure 7: Smith Chart of the proposed antenna.

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